

EFFECT OF BOSUBALL TRAINING ON VO2 MAX AMONG COLLEGE FOOTBALL PLAYERS

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Abstract:

The study sought to determine the effect of bosuball training on VO2 max in college football players. It was hypothesised that college football players' VO2 max would differ significantly as a result of bosuball training. For the current study, 30 male college football players from Malappuram district, Kerala state, India, were chosen at random, with ages ranging from 18 to 25 years. For the current study, a pre-test-post-test random group design with control and experimental groups was used. Group 'A' underwent bosuball training, while Group 'B' did not. The beep test was used to assess VO2 max. The data were gathered before and after twelve weeks of training. The data were analysed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The level of significance was set to 0.05. The bosuball training had positive impact on VO2 max and agility among college football players.

Key Words: Bosuball Training, VO2 Max, Football

Introduction:

The researcher believes that the Bosu ball is one of the modern assisting tools in the field of physical fitness that affects the development of aerobic capacity, which in turn has a significant obvious effect on physical performance and promoting physical and functional efficiency, and thus affects game performance, development, and mastery. Football is played in two formats: a 90-minute game with a 15-minute haltime break, and a more explosive 5-a-side game. Because this is a fast-paced sport, player fitness and strength are important, but so are high ball skills and game knowledge. Football's simplicity masks the intense physical requirements for success. Simply playing football by the hour will make a player better, but it is the focused and specialised training, directed at every segment of the player's required skill set, that will take a good player to the next level of ability and accomplishment.

Methodology:

The study sought to determine the effect of bosuball training on VO2 max in college football players. It was hypothesised that college football players' VO2 max would differ significantly as a result of bosuball training. For the current study, 30 male college football players from Malappuram district, Kerala state, India, were chosen at random, with ages ranging from 18 to 25 years. For the current study, a pre-test-post-test random group design with control and experimental groups was used. Group 'A' underwent bosuball training, while Group 'B' did not. The beep test was used to assess VO2 max. The data were gathered before and after twelve weeks of training. The data were analysed using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The level of significance was set to 0.05.

Results:

Table 1: ANCOVA between Experimental Group and Control Group on VO2 max of College football players for Pre, Post and Adjusted Test

	Experimental Group	Control Group	Source of Variance	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F
Pre Test Mean	41.04	40.76	BG	0.06	1	0.06	0.03
			WG	52.46	28	1.87	
Post Test Mean	44.59	40.90	BG	165.03	1	165.03	65.48*
			WG	70.56	28	2.52	
Adjusted Post Mean	44.50	40.89	BG	155.56	1	155.56	75.14*
			WG	55.98	27	2.07	

* Significant at 0.05 level.

df: 1/27= 4.21

Table 1 revealed that the obtained 'F' value of 75.14 was found to be significant at 0.05 level with df 1, 27 as the tabulated value of 4.21 required to be significant at 0.05 level. The same table indicated that there was a

significant difference in adjusted means of VO₂ max of college football players between experimental group and control group. The graphical representation of data has been presented in figure 1.

Figure 1: Comparisons of Pre - Test Means Post - Test Means and Adjusted Post - Test Means for Control group and Experimental Group in relation to VO₂ max

Conclusion:

The bosuball training had positive impact on VO₂ max and agility among college football players.

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